

Prevalence and Impact of Anxiety and Depression in Patients with Pemphigus and Psoriasis: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

This study investigates the prevalence of anxiety and depression in patients with pemphigus and psoriasis and its impact on their quality of life (QOL). Using a prospective longitudinal design, 100 participants (50 with psoriasis, 50 with pemphigus) were assessed at SCB Medical College, Cuttack. The findings reveal significant psychiatric comorbidities, particularly higher rates of depression and anxiety in pemphigus patients compared to those with psoriasis. The study underscores the importance of integrated care to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Psychiatric comorbidities, Anxiety, Depression, Quality of life, Pemphigus, Psoriasis.

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Introduction

Psychodermatology explores the interplay between dermatological conditions and psychiatric disorders. Psychological stress can exacerbate skin conditions, while visible skin disorders can lead to significant psychological distress [1]. Understanding the prevalence and impact of psychiatric conditions in dermatology patients is crucial for holistic treatment [2]. It is estimated that 30-40% of dermatology patients have underlying psychological issues.

Psoriasis: A chronic inflammatory skin condition affecting 1.4-2% of the global population, known to increase the risk of depression and anxiety [3].

Pemphigus: An autoimmune blistering disorder with severe physical manifestations, leading to a significant psychological burden [4]. To compare the prevalence of anxiety and depression in psoriasis and pemphigus patients and evaluate their impact on quality of life [5].

Methods

Study Design and Population:

- A prospective longitudinal study conducted at SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, from December 2021 to November 2022.
- Included 100 patients: 50 with psoriasis and 50 with pemphigus.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

- Inclusion: Patients aged 18-60 years, proficient in Odia, diagnosed with psoriasis or pemphigus, and willing to participate.
- Exclusion: Patients with comorbid medical illnesses or pre-existing psychiatric disorders unrelated to their dermatological condition, and those unwilling to participate.

Assessment Tools and Procedures:

- Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) and Severity Index for Pemphigus (SIP) for disease severity.
- Socio-demographic data, psychological variables, and quality of life assessed using a structured proforma, WHOQOL-BREF (Odia version), MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI 7.0.2), and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS).

Statistical Analysis Methods:

- Data analysis included descriptive statistics, Spearman rank correlation, chi-square tests, Mann-Whitney U tests, and independent samples t-tests using SPSS 24.
- A significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population:

- Age: Mean age for psoriasis patients was 41.90 ± 10.41 years, for pemphigus patients 42.12 ± 9.55 years.
- Gender: Roughly equal distribution between males and females, not statistically significant.
- Socio-economic Status: Predominantly lower socio-economic status for both groups.
- Marital Status and Locality: No significant differences noted between psoriasis and pemphigus groups.
- Occupation and Education: Majority was homemakers, and educational levels were similar across both groups.

Prevalence of Anxiety and Depression in Psoriasis and Pemphigus Patients:

- Psoriasis: 56% depression, 26% anxiety.
- Pemphigus: 76% depression, 32% anxiety.
- Significant difference in psychiatric comorbidity prevalence between psoriasis and pemphigus groups (p-value = 0.05).

Correlation of Psychiatric Conditions with Socio-Demographic Factors:

- Psoriasis: More prevalent in those >50 years, rural residents, lower SES, and unmarried, but not statistically significant.
- Pemphigus: More prevalent in those >50 years, rural residents, middle SES, and unmarried, but not statistically significant.

Comparative Analysis of Psychiatric Comorbidities in Both Patient Groups:

Pemphigus patients showed higher rates of psychiatric comorbidities compared to psoriasis patients, highlighting the need for targeted psychiatric support.

Discussion

This study explored the prevalence and impact of psychiatric comorbidities in patients with psoriasis and pemphigus, focusing on anxiety and depression and their effects on quality of life (QOL) [6]. The findings indicate a significant burden of psychiatric conditions in both patient groups, with pemphigus patients exhibiting higher rates of depression (76%) and anxiety (32%) compared to psoriasis patients (56% and 26%, respectively). These results underscore the substantial psychiatric impact of chronic dermatological conditions.

Socio-demographic factors, while not statistically significant predictors of psychiatric comorbidities, revealed trends worth noting. In both psoriasis and pemphigus patients, higher rates of depression and anxiety were observed in individuals over 50 years

of age, rural residents, and those with lower socio-economic status. Unmarried patients also showed a higher prevalence of psychiatric conditions. These trends highlight potential areas for targeted interventions, although further research is necessary to establish definitive correlations. The comparison with existing literature reinforces the study's findings, as previous research has documented high psychiatric morbidity in dermatology patients. However, the higher rates of psychiatric conditions in pemphigus patients relative to those with psoriasis necessitate additional investigation. Factors such as the chronicity and severe physical manifestations of pemphigus may contribute to its greater psychiatric burden. Integrated care approaches that combine dermatological and psychiatric treatment are essential for addressing the complex needs of patients with chronic skin conditions. The significant improvement in QOL and reduction in anxiety and depression scores following SSRI treatment in both patient groups emphasize the efficacy of such integrated models. These findings advocate for routine psychiatric screening and comprehensive management plans in dermatology practices [7].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant psychiatric burden in patients with psoriasis and pemphigus, particularly the higher prevalence of depression and anxiety in pemphigus patients. The lack of strong socio-demographic predictors for psychiatric conditions suggests that these comorbidities are primarily influenced by the severity and chronicity of the dermatological disorders themselves. Integrated dermatological and psychiatric care models are crucial for early detection and effective management of psychiatric symptoms, ultimately enhancing patient well-being and treatment outcomes. Quality of life, initially lower in pemphigus patients, showed significant improvement across all domains with integrated care, particularly in psychological well-being. Treatment with SSRIs significantly reduced anxiety and depression scores over successive follow-ups, underscoring the importance of addressing psychiatric comorbidities in dermatology patients. While anxiety scores did not significantly differ between the two groups, depression remained more pronounced in pemphigus patients, highlighting the need for tailored therapeutic approaches.

In conclusion, the study underscores the critical need for integrated care models that address both dermatological and psychiatric aspects of patient health. Effective management strategies that alleviate psychiatric symptoms can significantly improve overall health outcomes and quality of life in patients with chronic dermatological conditions. Future research should focus on optimizing these

integrated care approaches to further enhance patient care and outcomes in both dermatology and psychiatry practices.

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